

Wage Policy In Businesses As A Pioneer Of Organizational Commitment

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Abstract

Wage irregularity in organizations negatively affects the organizational belonging and organizational commitment of employees. If the necessary management and wage policies are not implemented by the employers, the needs of the employees are ignored and the necessary precautions are not taken, the employees either leave their jobs or harm the organization by not being able to focus on their work. For this reason, it is the primary duty of the employer to pay the wages regularly, to take the necessary precautions in case of unfavorable situations, and not to delay the wages of the employees.

Keywords: *Wage, Wage Policy, Organizational Commitment*

1. Introduction

Nowadays, in sectors that are in a rapid change and transformation; organizations, employees and the sectoral environment are significantly affected by changes and developments. With globalization, the rapid progress of the information age and the speed of change force organizations and employees to adapt in a competitive environment. These pressures cause physical and psychological discomfort on employees. Employees who cannot cope with the difficulties encountered due to work develop a negative attitude towards their workplace. The intention to leave the job is defined as the employee having a plan and thought of leaving his/her current job or workplace at a certain time (Fong and Mahfar, 2013: 35). Employees who have this plan and thought will evaluate the current conditions and form their expectations and will leave the job by putting their thoughts into action in line with the low level of fulfillment of these expectations (Polat and Meydan, 2010: 153). As employees who intend to leave of employment turn their intentions into activities, decreases in their organizational commitment will start in other employees.

Organizational commitment is a phenomenon that means employees' loyalty to the workplace, being in harmony, adopting and showing this with their behaviors. Organizational commitment is defined as the emotional commitment of the employee to the workplace. Business analyzes, business satisfaction and higher than expected performance levels are explained by the concept of commitment (Demirel, 2009:116). The concept of organizational commitment has a separate importance in terms of employee and employer. Business and individual are complementary to each other. Both individuals and organizations need each other to achieve their goals. A person can achieve his/her goals in the organization he/she is in, and he/she achieves his/her goals in the organization thanks to these people. Integrity will not be broken if there is unity (Seyhan, 2014: 16). Organizations all tend to increase their employees' commitment to their work and workplace. The most crucial factor that increases commitment is the wage system. For many years, the issue of wages has played an especially key role in the economic development, social development and political stability of a country. Therefore, very meticulous work is done on the wage. In fact, the issue of wages is becoming more complicated day by day and is the subject of scientific studies and discussions in many countries without losing its relevance and importance.

2. Wage

Wage, which is one of the basic concepts of economics, is the basic point of the relationship between the employee and the employer. The wage, which is a provision for labor among the production factors, is a cost item for the employer while it is the income it will provide for the employee (Esen et al. 2018-3 The concept of wages, which does not have a generally accepted definition, is defined differently in economic and social terms. Wages are accepted as a social right earned in the social state order. It is a price paid for the contributions of labor produced physically and intellectually to production (Acar, 2015: 4). As a broader and comprehensive definition, the wage is the amount that is determined in advance and should be paid to the employee by the employer, regardless of the profit or loss situation of the organization, without any condition such as the sale of the service or product produced (Işıkoğlu, 2017: 5).

Rigorous studies have been conducted on the concept of wages, which has been effective in the economic development, social development level and political decisions of countries for many years. As time progresses, the fee, which becomes more complex, remains up-to-date and is the subject of scientific research in countries. The concept of wages, which is the subject of the researches, increases the importance of the fact that it concerns more than one sector, that organizations attach importance to the issue in terms of protecting their own interests, that employees are a source of income, that justice can be achieved in wages among employees, and that organizations such as government interventions and trade unions focus too much on the issue (Ergül, 2006: 93).

The concept of fair wages was first articulated by Aquinas. The concept that forms the basis of today's wage approach is defined as 'the only wage that everyone can sustain themselves in their own class'. The concept of wages was defined as the wage of work, which was again paid as a minimum by Marx and Engels in the following years. Marx and Engels introduced a critical view of the capital system through the concept of wages. From the point of view, wage is the amount that the employee obtains in return for his/her labor but should be sufficient to sustain his/her life. From the point of view, there is injustice in the wages paid (Marks and Engels, 2013: 96).

The concept of wage, which is the Ottoman Turkish equivalent of 'ecir, is expressed with the words 'wage' in English and 'salaire' in French. In addition, instead of the concept of wage, it is used in terms such as rewarding, salary, payment, monthly, daily wage. The wage, which

realizes participation in economic activities, is also defined as a reward for the labor of both professional managers, entrepreneurs and laborers. When we look at the historical perspective, it is seen that the professionals who conduct entrepreneurial activities and the capital holders are separated. For this reason, it is paid in return for the intellectual labor of professionals who conduct entrepreneurial activities (Uyargil and Acar, 2019: 152). When examined from a legal point of view, wage is seen as the right that the employee receives in return for the employment contract. For this reason, wages are one of the basic elements of the employment contract. Wages are protected through state influence and collective bargaining agreements. In Article 55 of our Constitution, wages are defined as the compensation for labor. According to the Labor Law No. 4857, wage is the amount given to the employee by his/her employer or third parties in return for the work performed and paid in cash. On the other hand, by the International Labor Organization (ILO), wage is the amount that must be paid by the employer to the employee in accordance with the employment contract provided for the work performed or to be performed, which can be evaluated in monetary terms, as a result of mutual agreement or legally determined (Uyargil and Acar, 2019: 152).

When all definitions on the concept of wage are examined, it is accepted as the gain or price to be paid to the employee in return for the work performed or to be performed. However, determining the price is not as easy as determining the price of tangible assets. Because the reward for the labor performed at the same level in different sectors or fields is different. For example, even if the level of an employee working in the construction sector and an employee working in the textile sector is the same, their labor is different. For this reason, the number of wages to be paid for labor should also differ (Sabuncuoğlu, 2011: 244).

Determining the wage is a critical issue for organizations, employees, states, unions, society, economy and partners, in other words, for all parties. Because wages are a crucial step in terms of economic, social and political development (Çakır, 2006: 12).

For employees, wages are especially important in terms of maintaining their lives, providing psychological and social satisfaction, being the only source of livelihood as well as being financially satisfied. Employees are more interested in the economic side of the wage. Because wages play a key role in both improving the quality of life of employees and feeling safe. Therefore, the perception of wages for the employee varies according to how much it increases the quality of life (Sabuncuoğlu, 2000: 209). In addition, the fair and equal distribution of wages among employees is also especially important in terms of employee motivation. For this reason,

only the economical feature of the wage will not be sufficient to provide motivation. For some, wage motivation is provided by the increase in purchasing power, while for others it is provided by a fair and equal distribution. However, in general, wage ranks first as an effective factor in ensuring organizational commitment and increasing the motivation of employees (Benligiray, 2007: 10).

Wages are also especially important for the employer who wants to increase production efficiency and reduce costs. For this reason, all employers aim to employ quality and cheap labor. From the employer's point of view, wage is important in terms of keeping costs under control, ensuring performance evaluation, increasing productivity, making profit, increasing organizational commitment, providing motivation, creating appropriate wage policies and ensuring equal and fair distribution that will not cause legal difficulties (Çakır, 2006: 13). The point to be considered here is that employee performance is not reduced due to low wages. Because the performance of the employee who receives the wage that will satisfy him/her increases. The employee whose performance increases contributes more to the production process. As a result of this situation, the profitability of the business also increases. However, since the motivation of the employee with a low wage level cannot be fully achieved, his performance decreases (Işıkoğlu, 2002: 18). As a result, wage is an especially important phenomenon in terms of society and economy.

3. Organizational Commitment

The organization is defined as a community that fulfills the duties and responsibilities predetermined in line with a certain goal and tries to maximize the organizational goal (Öztürk, 2013: 7). The organization is a joint effort that arises from the cooperation between individuals and provides the opportunity to achieve goals that cannot be achieved individually. Organization is the formation that occurs when two or more individuals place their individual efforts, the tools and equipment they need in a certain order to achieve the common goals they have set (Aksun and Tokat, 2003: 115). In addition, the organization is defined as a management function in which the efforts of individuals are coordinated in line with the determined goals; a system in which human, target and technology dimensions are intertwined; and a structure that has a unique culture and shows the relationship between individuals and business processes. The efficiency and effectiveness of organizations play a key role in interpersonal relations

(Aydın, 2005: 116). Because the prerequisite for ensuring organizational effectiveness depends on the strength of the human element. Therefore, organizations gain meaning with the presence of individuals. At this point, organizations are in the position of supporting individual talents by making use of the limited but distinctive characteristics of individuals (Öztürk, 2013: 9). Different definitions have been made on the concept of organization. Some of these definitions are as follows. The organization is a system of forces consisting of two or more people and consisting of consciously planned activities (Barnard, 1994 as cited in Uslu, 2012: 12). The organization is the coordination of the activities conducted by people who have come together to realize a common purpose within the hierarchy of responsibility and authority by sharing tasks in business and business processes (Schein, 1970 as cited in Uslu, 2012: 12). Organizations are social units formed by individuals who come together to achieve predetermined goals. There is a social structure consisting of relationship between organizational members (Marc and Simon, 1958 as cited in Uslu, 2012: 12).

When we look at the definitions in general, the organization is expressed as the units formed because of the communication of voluntary individuals who will contribute to the processes to achieve a determined common goal. Different definitions have been made on the concept of organization, which is expressed with words such as 'organization' and 'institution' in the relevant literature, in terms of different branches of science such as economy, psychology, sociology, and politics. Therefore, it is not possible to make a simple, single and generalizable definition on the concept of organization (Şişman, 2002: 24). The organization is defined by Ülgen as an instrument that can be used by managers on the one hand and an environment in which the manager will be affected by the activities that will involve the manager on the other hand. In addition, the organization is the structure formed because of bringing together the material and non-material tools required for the production process in a systematic order (Ülgen, 2010: 52). As a result of the definitions made, the organization is a formation consisting of elements such as individuals, vehicles and machines, working conditions, financing conditions, buildings and establishment places within a structure and based on the relationships between these elements (Tutar et al. 2003: 61). The concept of addiction, on the other hand, refers to loyalty and an obligation to be fulfilled against a thought, individual, institution or a phenomenon that we see better than ourselves. Dependence is one of the most important and strongest feelings felt by employees towards institutions (Ardıç and Çöl, 2008: 157-170).

The concept of organizational commitment, which consists of the integration of the concepts of organization and dependency, expresses the employee's belief in the goals and values of the

organization, the effort that the organization wants to show for its goals, and the desire to continue as an organizational member (Mowday et al. 1979: 225). Today, the concept of organizational commitment, which has become an especially important concept and has been researched more than once, is a system approach focused on how to connect employees to the organization. The main reason organizational managers and researchers focus on this issue is the belief that employees with high commitment to the organization perform higher and have a low intention to quit (Bozkurt and Yurt, 2013: 122). In addition, organizational commitment has become a critical issue for researchers and managers since the end of the 1960s, as it is a concept that explains the effectiveness, efficiency and intention of employees to quit their jobs in the work environment (Özsoy, 2004: 15). Because the most important feature of the employees, who are accepted as the cornerstone of the organizations, is their ability to change. For this reason, the concept of organizational commitment has been tried to be explained by different authors and researchers with different definitions focusing on the efforts to ensure that employees stay in the organization. Organizational commitment is explained by the degree to which employees feel themselves as a part of this formation and the power union they have established with the organization (Balcı, 2003: 45). Organizational commitment is also expressed as the sum of internalized normative pressures to act in line with organizational interests. Organizational commitment refers to the power and loyalty attitude of the employees' emotional commitment to the organization (Özutku, 2008: 85).

When the development of the concept of organizational commitment in the historical process is examined, it is seen that the emotional and emotional commitment of the employees to the organization is first discussed. Today, organizational commitment is defined as the psychological commitment of employees to the organization they work for (Öztürk, 2013: 7).

In the historical process, commitment has been defined as the employees' adopting the goals of the organization they work for, feeling themselves belonging to the organization and feeling themselves as a member of a strong family within the organization. In addition, the concept of organizational commitment also represents the strength of the bond that employees have with the organization. The effort of the employee for the success of the organization and the sense of loyalty he/she develops towards the organization reveal the power of commitment (Çekmecelioğlu, 2006: 156).

Institutions that succeed in achieving organizational commitment gain multiple advantages. These advantages are listed as follows:

Organizational commitment increases the performance of employees.

Organizational commitment increases the motivation and loyalty level of the employees.

Organizational commitment prevents the development of negative behaviors and attitudes within the organization.

Organizational commitment provides internal integrity.

Organizational commitment supports the improvement of service quality.

Organizational commitment ensures employee continuity that strives to achieve organizational goals (Steers, 1997: 50).

There are multiple factors that will increase the commitment of employees to the organization. These factors are listed as providing financial opportunities (wages, premiums, etc.), organizing cultural activities, developing equal and fair management policies, showing leadership, supporting the employee to establish a balance between work life and private life, employing employees in the field suitable for their individual abilities and characteristics, and supporting the development of employees through in-service training (Doğan and Kılıç, 2007: 39; Çöl, 2004: 6).

Organizational commitment provides employees with the opportunity to become a member of the organization by integrating with the institution they work for, identifying with the organization, making sacrifices for the interests of the organization, adopting the goals of the organization and making efforts, and developing loyalty to the organization (Koç, 2009: 203).

If employees can achieve their own goals, they strive for organizational goals and increase their commitment to the organization. For this reason, to increase the productivity of the employees, it is necessary to adopt the organizational goals and ensure their organizational commitment. Because organizational commitment is the most important force that ensures the success of organizations (Ersoy and Bayraktaroğlu, 2010: 15).

Employees, who show loyalty and commitment to the organization, act with the awareness of being a part of the organization and make an increasing contribution both qualitatively and qualitatively to achieve the goals of the organization (İşcan and Atılhan, 2004: 185).

4. Organizational Commitment and Wage Policy

The wages of the employees in return for the work they perform are also guaranteed by the laws and the legal legislation has given some rights to the employees. These rights are.

- The employee, who decides to leave the job due to wage irregularity, is entitled to compensation because he has terminated with just cause.
- Employees who continue their work during the wage irregularity have the right to abstain from work.

If the employees abstain from work and slow down their work, there will be disruptions in the processes. These disruptions can be felt more seriously in some sectors. For example, the fact that an employee working in the health sector slows down his/her work, cannot be motivated for his/her job or avoids work jeopardizes human health and even public health. For this reason, employers should be sensitive about wages (Saygılı, 2019: 25).

It is assumed that employees with wage irregularities cannot meet their basic needs. Because after the wage received meets the necessary needs of the employees, steps such as upper step security, belonging and self-realization, which Maslow describes in his theory, are started. For this reason, the wage irregularity causes the physiological needs not to be met (Keser, 2014: 21). As a result, employees who experience wage irregularity.

- Organizational commitment,
- The bonds of trust they have for the organization,
- Sense of belonging,
- Sense of justice and equality, and
- Their performance will be negatively affected and diminished.

Employees who experience wage irregularity also must disrupt their payments in their private life, interest is applied to bank debts whose payments are deferred, they are in a mental crisis in case of non-payment of wages and uncertainty about when to pay. The most justified result of the wage irregularity, which cannot overcome this problem and is constantly experienced by

the employer, is the justified termination according to the Labor Law No. 4857 (Saygılı, 2019: 26).

CONCLUSION

Wage, which is the main source of income for employees, is seen as both a cost and motivation tool for managers. Wages are not only a tool to meet the physical needs of employees, but also an essential element in meeting their social and psychological needs. Experiencing wage satisfaction by employees enables them to develop positive attitudes towards their organization. Wage satisfaction, which contributes positively to employees in terms of motivation and performance, also contributes to increasing organizational efficiency and effectiveness. At the same time, employee performance is important for organizations to compete effectively and achieve the goals they set. Because the factor that plans the processes and activities of the organizations, gains the competitive power and ensures the access to the targets is human. For this reason, organizations need to have a healthy, happy and dynamic employee structure in order to continue their existence, grow and develop.

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